

STRUCTURAL, MORPHOLOGICAL AND MICROMECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF GELATIN-BACTERIAL CELLULOSE NATURAL COMPOSITES

Franck Quero¹, Abigail Coveney^{2,3}, Anna E. Lewandowska⁴, Paulo Díaz-Calderón¹, Robert M. Richardson², Koon-Yang Lee⁵, Stephen J. Eichhorn⁴, M. Ashraf Alam² and Javier Enrione¹

¹ Biopolymer Research and Engineering Lab (BiopREL), Department of Nutrition and Dietetics, Universidad de los Andes, Av. Monseñor Álvaro del Portillo 12.455, Las Condes, Santiago, Chile
Email: franck.quero@uandes.cl, web page: <http://www.uandes.cl>

² Bristol Centre for Functional Nanomaterials, Centre for NSQI, University of Bristol, Tyndall Avenue, Bristol BS8 1FD, UK
Email: abigail.coveney@bristol.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.bcnf.bris.ac.uk>

³ H.H. Wills Physics Laboratory, University of Bristol, Tyndall Avenue, Bristol BS8 1TL, UK
Email: a.alam@bristol.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.bris.ac.uk>

⁴ Department of Engineering, University of Exeter, Exeter EX4 4QL, UK
Email: s.j.eichhorn@exeter.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.exeter.ac.uk>

⁵ The Composite Centre, Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College, South Kensington Campus, London SW7 2AZ, UK
Email: koonyang.lee@imperial.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.imperial.ac.uk>

Keywords: Gelatin, Bacterial cellulose, Composites, Interfaces

ABSTRACT

The effect of adding bacterial cellulose (BC) to gelatin was investigated. Structural and morphological information from the resulting composite materials was obtained from powder X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy and 2D Raman imaging, revealing an in-homogeneous dispersion of BC within the gelatin matrix. The optical properties of the composite materials were investigated by UV-visible spectrophotometry. The results showed that by adding 10 wt.% BC to gelatin, visible transparency was reduced by ~35 % and UV opacity was increased by ~40 %, compared to gelatin. For the first time, the molecular interaction between gelatin and BC was investigated by Raman spectroscopy showing that it is a relevant tool to quantify the micromechanical interfacial interaction between gelatin and BC.

1 INTRODUCTION

Materials obtained from renewable resources and potentially entirely biodegradable are currently attracting much attention [1]. Gelatin and bacterial cellulose (BC) belong to this class of materials but in addition of being obtain from renewable resource and being potentially fully biodegradable, these materials are generally edible making them ideal candidates to be used as edible food coatings and encapsulating agents. Gelatin, however, suffers from having poor mechanical properties and so its use for these applications is limited. Gelatin is, for example, particularly brittle [2] and lacks of mechanical robustness. On the contrary, BC is known to have good mechanical properties. Young's modulus and tensile strength of BC pellicles are respectively ~15 GPa and 260 MPa [3] and so BC has the potential to mechanically reinforce gelatin films. Consequently, by adding BC to gelatin, one could design robust edible food coatings and encapsulating agents. A question remains however open on if the potential of BC to reinforce gelatin could be fully realised.

There is currently very little information on the nature of the molecular interaction between gelatin and BC (and cellulose in general). Raman spectroscopy has been reported to be a relevant technique to quantify the molecular interaction between several forms of cellulose and polymer matrices such as, polylactic acid [4], polyvinyl acetate [5], epoxy resin [6] to cite a few examples only. Before applying this method, it is first necessary to verify the detection of the Raman band located at $\sim 1095\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to the vibrational motions of C-O and C-O-C moieties in the backbone structure of cellulose [7,8]. Adjusting the volume fraction of cellulose added within the polymer matrix can control the intensity of that Raman band [9]. As soon as the Raman band located at $\sim 1095\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be detected for accurate peak position determination, one can quantify the micromechanical interaction between cellulose and the host matrix. This method consists in monitoring the position of the Raman band initially located at $\sim 1095\text{ cm}^{-1}$ upon application of external tensile deformation. It is currently unknown if this method can be used to quantify the interfacial interaction within gelatin-matrix composites. This is also what this study aims to investigate.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Bovine gelatin type B was purchased from Rousselot (Sao Paulo, Brazil). Dried bacterial cellulose was kindly provided by Membracel (Curitiba, Brazil). Silica gel was purchased from Winkler Ltda (Santiago, Chile). All materials and chemicals were used as received with no further purification.

2.2 Materials

First of all, 5 g of dried BC was soaked overnight in 1.2 L of deionised water. The next day, the water/BC mixture was blended using a kitchen blender (Thomas "Premium") for 20 min. The mixture was then filtered gravimetrically using paper filter (WhatmanTM 541) and a BC filter cake was obtained. This filter cake contained $\sim 2\text{ wt.}\%$ BC. A gelatin solution (7% w/v) was then prepared by dissolving 10.5 g of gelatin powder in deionised water for 1h at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A controlled amount of the BC filter cake was then added to the gelatin solution, which was stirred for one hour at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The pH of the suspension was adjusted to ~ 5 (isoelectric point of gelatin) [10] by adding small amounts of sodium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid solutions. In order to obtain gelatin-BC films, 20 mL of the suspensions was poured into Petri dishes and allowed to dry for 2 weeks at $5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. At the end of the drying process, composite materials having BC concentrations of 0.5, 2, 6 and 10 wt.% based on the dried weight of gelatin were obtained. The films were carefully removed from the polystyrene Petri dishes and conditioned for 1 month with silica gel.

2.3 Crystalline structure by powder X-ray diffraction

The crystalline structure of gelatin and gelatin-BC composites was determined by powder X-ray diffraction. An X-ray diffractometer (Phillips X'Pert Pro) having a $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation source was used to monitor crystallographic data from $2\theta = 5^\circ$ to 50° with step size of 0.02° . The current was set to 30 mA and the acceleration voltage to 40 kV. The area under the diffraction peak located at $2\theta = 9^\circ$ was determined by fitting the spectra with a Lorentzian function (PeakFit v4.12). These areas were normalised to the weight fraction of BC of the composite materials. Experiments were performed in triplicate and so averages and standard deviation data are reported.

2.4 Morphology observation by SEM and 2D Raman imaging

The cross-section and surface/subsurface morphology of gelatin and gelatin-BC composites were observed by respectively scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and 2D Raman imaging.

First of all, the samples were gold coated using a diode magnetron sputtering coater and subsequently fixed onto metal stubs using carbon tabs. SEM imaging of cryofracture surfaces of gelatin and gelatin-BC composite films was carried out using an EVO MA 10 Carl Zeiss electron microscope at an acceleration voltage of 25 kV.

2D Raman imaging was performed using an XploraTM Plus Raman microscope (Horiba, France). Images were obtained by using a laser source having a wavelength of 785 nm (diameter of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$). The Raman spectrometer was equipped with an optical microscope having a 50 \times long working distance objective (PL Fluotar, numerical aperture 0.55). These characteristics of the system resulted in a spatial resolution of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$. Surface/subsurface mappings were carried out using a motorized stage. A multivariate analysis referred to as classical least square (CLS) method was used to generate the 2D Raman images.

2.5 Thermal properties by DSC and TGA

A Perkin Elmer Pyris 1 power compensation DSC was used to assess the enthalpy of melting of gelatin and gelatin-BC composites. This information was obtained from the first heating curve. Each sample, having a weight of $\sim 15 \text{ mg}$ was inserted in a $30 \mu\text{L}$ medium pressure stainless steel pan. Each sample was cooled down from room temperature to $-30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at a cooling rate of $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Each sample was kept at $-30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 min and subsequently heated from $-30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ up to $190 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Each sample was then cooled down again and finally re-heated in the same conditions. Experiments were triplicated and values for the enthalpy of melting of the materials are averages and standard deviations. Enthalpy of melting values were normalised by the weight fraction of BC for the composite materials.

TGA was performed to determine the degradation properties of gelatin, gelatin-BC composites and BC. Each analysis was performed using a 5-10 mg sample, which were heated from room temperature up to $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ in a platinum crucible under a nitrogen gas flow of 40 mL min^{-1} . The onset and peak degradation temperatures were obtained from the first derivative of the weight loss as a function of temperature (dm/dT). Experiments were triplicated and averages and standard deviations are reported.

2.6 Optical properties by UV-visible spectrophotometry

The optical properties of gelatin and gelatin-BC composites were measured by UV-visible spectrophotometry. A Hitachi spectrophotometer was used to quantify the transmittance in the light wavelength range of 200 to 1000 nm and using steps of 50 nm. Surface areas of the gelatin and gelatin-BC composite films were selected so that no significant different between their thickness was measured. These areas had thicknesses of $0.16 \pm 0.01 \text{ mm}$.

2.7 Micromechanical interfacial interaction by Raman spectroscopy

The micromechanical interfacial interaction between gelatin and BC was quantified by Raman spectroscopy. A Renishaw Raman spectrometer (RM 1000 system), having a 785 nm wavelength laser, was utilised to obtain Raman spectra from gelatin and gelatin-BC composites. The Raman band located at $\sim 1095 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was only detectable with a sufficiently high intensity at a BC concentration of 10 wt.%. Consequently, the micromechanical study was performed only for those composite materials. Composite films having dimensions of $\sim 20 \times 10 \times 0.1 \text{ mm}$ were deformed in tensile mode using a customised deformation rig fitted with a 200 N load cell. A Raman spectrum was obtained at each 0.02 mm extension step in the Raman shift range of 1050 to 1150 cm^{-1} . The positions of the Raman band initially located at $\sim 1095 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were determined using a Lorentzian function and an algorithm based on the work of Marquardt [11]. The positions of the Raman band located at $\sim 1095 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were plotted as a function of tensile strain and stress. In order to quantify the micromechanical interaction the data were fitted with linear equations and the slope reported and expressed in $\text{cm}^{-1}\%^{-1}$ and $\text{cm}^{-1}\text{GPa}^{-1}$ is a measure of the micromechanical interaction between gelatin and BC. Experiments were triplicated and so the results are reported as average and standard deviation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 reports typical X-ray diffraction patterns for gelatin and gelatin-BC composites. The pattern for gelatin is characterised by a diffraction peak located at $\sim 2\theta = 9^\circ$. This peak has been

reported before and corresponds to the presence of triple helix configurations in the gelatin matrix^{2,12}. The intensity of that diffraction peak has been reported to be directly proportional to the triple helix content in gelatin. A broad hump starting from $\sim 2\theta = 12^\circ$ and finishing at $\sim 2\theta = 32^\circ$ has also been reported before for gelatin and corresponds to its amorphous fraction^{2,12}. Then, when BC is added to gelatin, one can observe the presence of the typical diffraction peaks of cellulose I, with typical diffraction planes of (101), (10 $\bar{1}$) and (002). As expected, the intensity of these diffraction peaks increases when the BC concentration increases.

Interestingly, no diffraction planes coming from the BC is interfering with the diffraction peak of gelatin located at $\sim 2\theta = 9^\circ$. This allows studying if BC could prevent or favour the formation of the triple helix configuration of the gelatin fraction in the composite materials (see inset in Figure 1). Table 1 reports the normalised area under the diffraction peak of gelatin located at $\sim 2\theta = 9^\circ$ as a function of the BC weight fraction. No significant difference is reported here, suggesting that the presence of BC in gelatin does not prevent or neither favour the formation of the triple helix configuration during film formation. This observation was also confirmed by the determination of the normalised enthalpy of melting of gelatin and gelatin-BC composites by DSC, which is also directly proportional to the amount of triple helix configuration in gelatin. No significant difference in triple helix configuration content was observed upon increase the BC concentration as reported in Table 1.

Figure 1: Typical XRD patterns obtained for gelatin (Ge) and gelatin-bacterial cellulose (BC) composites. The inset represents the diffraction peak from the gelatin phase located at $\sim 2\theta = 9^\circ$.
"Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, Just Accepted Manuscript.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society."

Bacterial cellulose content (wt.%)	Normalised integrated peak area at $\sim 2\theta = 9^\circ$ (arbitrary units / $^\circ$)	Normalised enthalpy of melting, ΔH_m (J g ⁻¹)
0	4 ± 2	18 ± 1
0.5	5 ± 2	18 ± 2
2	7 ± 1	18 ± 0
6	6 ± 1	17 ± 0
10	3 ± 3	16 ± 1

Table 1: Normalised areas under the peak from the gelatin phase located at $\sim 2\theta = 9^\circ$, obtained by XRD and normalised enthalpy of melting of the gelatin phase, obtained by DSC. "Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, Just Accepted Manuscript.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society."

Figure 2 reports typical TGA traces for gelatin, gelatin-BC composites and BC. One can observe a significant shift of the onset and peak degradation temperatures upon increasing of the BC concentration. This is supported by detailed information reported in Table 2. This result is of importance if one wants to process these materials at high temperature, including spray-drying or extrusion. No significant changes in weight loss at 500 °C were observed.

Figure 2: TGA traces obtained for bacterial cellulose (BC), gelatin (Ge) and gelatin-BC composites. The grey and black arrows indicate, respectively, a significant shift towards a higher temperature of the onset and peak degradation temperature. The inset shows similar data from a temperature range of 225 to 375 °C. “Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, Just Accepted Manuscript.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society.”

Bacterial cellulose content (wt.%)	Onset degradation temperature (°C)	Peak degradation temperature, T_{peak} (°C)	Weight loss at 500°C (%)
0	266 ± 1	314 ± 4	77 ± 2
0.5	269 ± 2	315 ± 3	75 ± 2
2	272 ± 1	319 ± 2	76 ± 4
6	275 ± 2	321 ± 2	69 ± 2
10	278 ± 1	330 ± 2	71 ± 3
100	318 ± 1	352 ± 2	78 ± 6

Table 2: Detailed TGA data obtained for bacterial cellulose (BC), gelatin (Ge) and gelatin-BC composites. Onset, peak degradation temperature and weight loss at 500 °C are reported. “Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, Just Accepted Manuscript.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society.”

Figure 3 reports SEM images of the morphology of cryofracture surfaces of gelatin and gelatin-BC composites (2 and 10 wt.%). Gelatin seems to display a form of layered structure while images of the composite materials also display a layered structure with a combination of BC aggregates (Figure 3b)

and BC fibrils (Figure 3c) entrapped in between gelatin layers. This suggests a relatively poor dispersion of BC within the gelatin matrix, throughout the thickness of the films.

Figure 3: SEM images showing the cross-section morphology of (a) gelatin (Ge) and (b) and (c) gelatin-BC composites (2 and 10 wt.%). White and black arrows show the gelatin and BC phases respectively. "Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, Just Accepted Manuscript.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society."

Figure 4 reports 2D Raman images from the surface/subsurface of gelatin-BC composite films. For all the sample composition, it is clear that a poor dispersion was obtained at the sample surface and so BC is inhomogeneously dispersed in the gelatin matrix. At a 6 wt.% BC weight fraction, the dispersion seems to be best. At a 10 wt.% BC weight fraction, it is possible that the system phase separated during film formation although this has not been directly evidenced. These images may also contain information from the subsurface since the laser having a wavelength of 785 nm used can penetrate into the samples up to a maximum depth of $\sim 12 \mu\text{m}$. This means that the surface aggregation observed in these images might be slightly overestimated.

Figure 4: 2D images obtained from gelatin-BC composites with weight fractions of (a) 0.5 %, (b) 2 %, (c) 6 % and (d) 10 %. The images provide morphological information from the surface and subsurface of the composite films. "Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, Just Accepted Manuscript.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society."

Figure 5 shows UV-visible transmittance data for gelatin and gelatin-BC composites. In the visible wavelength range (400-700 nm), one can see that the transmittance significantly decreases upon addition of BC to the gelatin matrix. At a 10 wt.% BC weight fraction, the transparency is still relatively well preserved and the composites films still show some good degree of transparency. In the UV wavelength range (200-400 nm), the transmittance is also significantly reduced upon addition of BC to the gelatin matrix. This suggests that when adding BC to the gelatin matrix, the composite films are able to better filter-out UV light. This is directly related to SEM and 2D Raman images since BC agglomerates may be able to scatter UV light and so they act as a UV light barrier. This observation is particularly interesting if one consider using these composite materials as transparent food coatings or encapsulating agents for UV sensitive foodstuff or compounds. Consequently, for that specific property, aggregates are actually an advantage.

Figure 5: Transmittance measured for gelatin (Ge) and gelatin-BC composites as a function of wavelength. The grey and black arrows indicate, respectively, an improvement of UV light opacity and a reduction of visible light transparency. "Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, Just Accepted Manuscript.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society."

The mechanical properties of these gelatin-BC composite films are also of importance in addition to the optical properties. In this study, instead of studying the tensile mechanical performance of these materials, as a macroscopic property, the micromechanical interaction between gelatin and BC was studied instead. This is the first study reported so far to quantify the molecular interaction between gelatin and cellulose. This method relies on following the shift of the Raman band located at ~ 1095 cm^{-1} belonging to cellulose as a function of strain and stress. This allows following the molecular deformation of cellulose embedded in the gelatin matrix and so provides information about the interfacial micromechanical interaction between cellulose and gelatin.

Figure 7 reports typical Raman spectra for gelatin and gelatin-BC composites in the Raman shift range of 1050 to 1150 cm^{-1} . No Raman peak is present for gelatin in that range and so one can conclude that gelatin and BC are spectroscopically distinct in that Raman shift range. By adding BC to the gelatin matrix, one can see an increase of the intensity of the Raman band located at 1095 cm^{-1} . At a BC weight fraction of 10 wt.%, the intensity was found to be sufficiently high to be able to accurately determine the peak position of the Raman band located at ~ 1095 cm^{-1} .

Figure 8 reports a typical shift of the Raman band initially located at ~ 1095 cm^{-1} towards a lower wavenumber upon applying a 5% tensile strain.

Figure 7: Typical Raman spectra obtained from gelatin (Ge) and gelatin-bacterial cellulose (BC) composite films in the Raman shift range of 1050 to 1150 cm^{-1} . "Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, Just Accepted Manuscript.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society."

Figure 8: Typical shift towards a lower wavenumber of the Raman band initially located at $\sim 1095 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ upon applying an external tensile deformation to a composite materials containing 10 wt.% BC. "Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society."

Figure 9 reports detailed shifts of the Raman band initially located at $\sim 1095\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as a function of strain. Significant shifts were found to occur. The relationship between the Raman band shift and strain was found to be linear. Consequently, the data were fitted with linear equations. Two domains were identified with at first the gradient to the data having a value of $-0.73\text{ cm}^{-1}\%^{-1}$. The second domain was found to have a gradient of $-0.27\text{ cm}^{-1}\%^{-1}$. From three repeated experiments, the average gradients for these two domains were found to be, respectively, $-0.63 \pm 0.20\text{ cm}^{-1}\%^{-1}$ and $-0.25 \pm 0.03\text{ cm}^{-1}\%^{-1}$. This change of gradient, occurring at $\sim 1.5\%$, might be indicative of some interfacial debonding between BC and gelatin. In inset from Figure 9 is a stress-strain curve that was recorded during the very same Raman micromechanical deformation tests. One can identify a linear region from 0 to 1% strain and then a non-linear domain. The transition between that linear and non-linear behaviour is usually referred as the yield point and is occurring at $\sim 1.5\%$. Consequently the change of slope observed for the Raman band shift as a function of strain may be related to interfacial debonding occurring close to when the yield point is reached.

Figure 9. Detailed shifts of the Raman band initially located at $\sim 1095\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as a function of strain for a composite containing 10 wt.% BC. The inset is a typical stress-strain curve obtained from the same composite material. "Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, Just Accepted Manuscript.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society."

Figure 10 reports detailed shifts of the Raman band located at $\sim 1095\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as a function of stress. One can observe a linear relationship between those shifts with respect to stress. By fitting the data with a linear equation, the gradient of fit was found to be $-29\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{GPa}^{-1}$. From three repeats, the gradient of fit was found to be $-27 \pm 3\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{GPa}^{-1}$. By normalising the data to the volume fraction of BC in the composite material (10 wt.% here), this corresponds to a gradient of fit of $-3.9 \pm 0.4\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{GPa}^{-1}\text{vol.}\%^{-1}$, which is higher than the value of $-2.5\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{GPa}^{-1}\text{vol.}\%^{-1}$ obtained for PLA-BC composites [4]. This suggests a stronger interaction between BC and gelatin compared to BC and PLA. This might be related to the fact that gelatin and BC can potentially form relatively strong interfacial hydrogen bonding. On the contrary, the interaction between BC (hydrophilic) and PLA (hydrophobic) is expected to be relatively weak.

Figure 10. Detailed shifts of the Raman band initially located at $\sim 1095\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as a function of stress for a composite containing 10 wt.% BC. “Reproduced with permission from [Quero, F.; Coveney, A.; Lewandowska, A. E.; Richardson, R. M.; Díaz Calderón, P.; Lee, K.-Y.; Eichhorn, S. J.; Alam, M. A.; Enrione, J. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, Just Accepted Manuscript.] Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society.”

4 CONCLUSIONS

Gelatin-BC composites were prepared by cold solvent casting with weight fractions of 0.5, 2, 6 and 10 wt.% BC. SEM and 2D Raman imaging revealed a poor dispersion of BC within the gelatin matrix. As expected, UV-visible spectrophotometry showed a loss of visible transparency upon addition of BC. In the UV light range, the UV transparency also decreased meaning that the films were showing a significant improvement of UV light opacity. This property is particularly interesting if those films are to be used as food coatings or encapsulating agent for UV sensitive products.

Raman spectroscopy was found to be a relevant tool to study the interfacial micromechanical interaction between gelatin and BC. First, we demonstrated that gelatin and BC were spectroscopically distinct in the Raman shift range of 1050 to 1150 cm^{-1} . Also, by adjusting the BC concentration to 10 wt.%, the Raman band located at $\sim 1095\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was found to be detectable with a sufficiently high intensity for accurate determination of its peak position while applying external tensile deformation. Significant shifts towards a lower wavenumber were found to occur upon application of external tensile deformation, which suggested that stress is being transferred from the gelatin matrix to the BC reinforcement.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

F.Q. and J.E. would like to thank FONDECYT (Chile) under the grants N° 3140036 and N° 1140132 respectively and A.C. the EPSRC (UK) under the grant N° EP/G036780/1 for financial support.

REFERENCES

- [1] S.J. Eichhorn, A. Gandini, Materials from Renewable Resources, *MRS Bulletin*, **35**, 2010, pp. 187-193 (doi: [10.1557/mrs2010.650](https://doi.org/10.1557/mrs2010.650)).

- [2] I. Yakimets, N. Wellner, A.C. Smith, R.H. Wilson, I. Farhat, J. Mitchell, Mechanical properties with respect to water content of gelatin films in glassy state, *Polymer*, **46**, 2005, pp. 12577-12585 (doi:[10.1016/j.polymer.2005.10.090](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2005.10.090)).
- [3] S. Yamanaka, K. Watanabe, N. Kitamura, M. Iguchi, S. Mitsuhashi, Y. Nishi, M. Uryu, The structure and mechanical properties of sheets prepared from bacterial cellulose, *Journal of Materials Science*, **24**, 1989, pp. 3141-3145 (doi: [10.1007%2F01139032](https://doi.org/10.1007%2F01139032)).
- [4] F. Quero, M. Nogi, H. Yano, K. Abdulsalami, S.M. Holmes, B.H. Sakakini, S.J. Eichhorn, Optimization of the Mechanical Performance of Bacterial Cellulose/Poly(l-lactic Acid) Composites, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, **2**, 2009, pp. 321-330 (doi:[10.1021/am900817f](https://doi.org/10.1021/am900817f)).
- [5] R. Rusli, K. Shanmuganathan, S.J. Rowan, C. Weder, S.J. Eichhorn, Stress-Transfer in Anisotropic and Environmentally Adaptive Cellulose Whisker Nanocomposites, *Biomacromolecules*, **11**, 2010, pp. 762-768 (doi: [10.1021/bm1001203](https://doi.org/10.1021/bm1001203)).
- [6] R. Rusli, S.J. Eichhorn, Determination of the stiffness of cellulose nanowhiskers and the fiber-matrix interface in a nanocomposite using Raman spectroscopy, *Applied Physics Letters*, **93**, 2008, 033111 (doi: [10.1063/1.2963491](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2963491)).
- [7] N. Gierlinger, M. Schwanninger, A. Reinecke, I. Burgert, Molecular Changes during Tensile Deformation of Single Wood Fibers Followed by Raman Microscopy, *Biomacromolecules*, **7**, 2006, pp. 2077-2081 (doi: [10.1021/bm060236g](https://doi.org/10.1021/bm060236g)).
- [8] J.H. Wiley, R.H. Atalla, Band assignments in the raman spectra of celluloses, *Carbohydrate Research*, **160**, 1987, pp. 113-129 (doi: [10.1016/0008-6215\(87\)80306-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0008-6215(87)80306-3)).
- [9] R. Rusli, Interfacial micromechanics of natural cellulose whisker polymer nanocomposites using Raman spectroscopy. University of Manchester, Manchester, 2011:PhD Thesis.
- [10] P. Díaz-Calderón, L. Caballero, F. Melo, J. Enrione, Molecular configuration of gelatin–water suspensions at low concentration, *Food Hydrocolloids*, **39**, 2014, pp. 171-179 (doi: [10.1016/j.foodhyd.2013.12.019](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2013.12.019)).
- [11] D.W. Marquardt, An Algorithm for Least-Squares Estimation of Nonlinear Parameters, *Journal of the Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics*, **11**, 1963, pp. 431-441 (doi: [10.1137/0111030](https://doi.org/10.1137/0111030)).
- [12] A. Bigi, S. Panzavolta, K. Rubini, Relationship between triple-helix content and mechanical properties of gelatin films, *Biomaterials*, **25**, 2004, pp. 5675-5680 (doi: [10.1016/j.biomaterials.2004.01.033](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2004.01.033)).